

Reducing energy consumption and processing time by smart robot-workpiece position planning in robotic manufacturing processes

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Abstract

This paper presents a novel method for pre-processing optimization of robot-workpiece configuration in manufacturing processes based on a continuous end-effector toolpath with a defined feed-rate. Industrial robots are widely used in applications involving low cutting forces (such as additive manufacturing, grinding, polishing, abrasive waterjet and laser cutting, welding, and large-format 3D printing) especially to produce complex-shaped parts. As the adoption of such processes increases, so does their contribution to energy consumption in manufacturing. Unlike conventional methods based on inverse dynamics or data-driven models, the proposed approach leverages the robot's kinetic energy profile and its integral along the toolpath as an optimization criterion. This simplification significantly reduces computational effort while maintaining sufficient accuracy to distinguish between different configurations. A genetic algorithm (type of evolutionary algorithm) is used to minimize kinetic energy and, consequently, power consumption. A key innovation of the method lies in its ability to determine the optimal mutual position of the robot and the workpiece for the entire process motion of the end-effector, in contrast to existing approaches that typically address auxiliary movements. Experimental validation performed with two industrial robots and two different manufacturing processes using a rotary-tilting table showed energy savings of up to 9.6%. These results confirm the method's effectiveness and its potential for wide industrial application.

Keywords

Robotics; Energy consumption; Configuration optimization; Genetic algorithm; Continuous toolpath

1. Introduction

Several complex shaped parts may be produced using technologies that generate no or minimal process forces. For example, laser or abrasive waterjet cutting can be used to cut or sculpt complex shaped parts from plastic materials, composite or metallic materials, like stainless steel [1]. Abrasive waterjet cutting is a suitable technology to produce complex shaped parts, offering proper surface finish quality, high precision and reduction of waste material and secondary process operations compared to, for example, conventional cutting as described by [2]. Complex shaped parts produced by abrasive waterjet or laser cutting technology may include, for instance:

- parts carved with a technological bevel (e.g. bevel gears);
- shaped structures lightened by cutting out excess material;
- dashboards and panels (e.g. automotive).

Another technology that does not emit large process forces is 3D printing technology, such as metal wire or powder deposition technology, either using a laser beam (LMD or L-DED), described e.g. in [3] and [4], or an electric arc (WAAM). The differences between various metal 3D printing technologies are described in more detail in [5], [6], [7] and [8], which show that accurate production of parts using WAAM technology requires carrying out corrections to the deposition trajectory and to the process parameter settings, especially in areas such as sharp corners or edges. The authors also present a mathematical model that can determine these corrections. Another technology from this group is large-format 3D printing [9]. It can be used for example to manufacture plastic parts from filament or plastic pellets reinforced with glass or carbon fibres – PEM, described in more detail in [10] or in [11]. In this case, an industrial robot can carry an extruder, which extrudes the molten plastic and forms the resulting part. Parts created using this technology can include, for instance:

- moulds for laminating composite parts (the mould must be further machined after printing);
- vacuum clamps for machining thin-walled parts;
- furniture or other design and construction accessories;
- complex shaped machine housings, or supporting structures for other equipment.

Since it can take hours or days to complete the printing of these parts, it is worth looking for an energy efficient process set-up. The setting of process parameters also plays a major role, as they affect both the surface quality and structural properties of the resulting part.

One of the key parameters to be monitored, especially in batch or mass production, is power consumption. According to [12], in 2017, industrial companies were responsible for approximately 36% of global energy consumption and industrial robots accounted for a significant part of this consumption. For example, the use of robots in the automotive industry is intensive and approximately 8% of the energy consumption in this sector is attributed to robots. Rising energy prices and stricter environmental regulations increase the need to optimize the energy consumption of robotic systems. Efficient processes optimized to consume less energy can significantly reduce production costs and the negative environmental impacts of production. The study presented in [13] summarises methods, strategies and technologies aimed at optimizing energy consumption in processes using industrial robots. According to the study, various approaches to reducing electrical energy consumption can be classified as follows:

- **Choosing the right robot** – the use of lighter and smaller robots with adequate carrying capacity reduces energy consumption. Robots with efficient motors, regenerative braking and low friction contribute to energy savings.
- **Energy efficient components** – using energy efficient motors can reduce energy consumption by up to 50%. One example is implementing regenerative braking to capture and reuse kinetic energy.
- **Programming optimization** – minimizing unnecessary movements, optimizing trajectory and feed-rate control. Use of simulations and machine learning algorithms to find the most energy efficient paths.
- **Energy monitoring and management** – deploying sensors and monitoring systems to track energy consumption in real time. Use of software to identify areas for improvement and optimize consumption during operation.
- **Energy saving management features** – implementing sleep modes or automatic shutdown when idle. Intelligent power management that adapts power and feed-rate to the actual task requirements.
- **Regular maintenance** – ensuring optimal component condition (e.g. lubrication of joints, replacement of worn parts) reduces energy losses due to friction.
- **Optimizing production processes** – minimizing unnecessary movements and optimizing material flow in production. Programming robots to adapt to environmental changes (e.g. temperature, humidity) and reduce energy consumption.

According to the study, other research directions for robotic technologies include the development of adaptive control strategies that respond to changes in the environment or the task being performed, application of artificial intelligence for data analysis and power consumption optimization, hardware improvements such as lightweight and efficient materials, and innovations in sensors. For example, [14] presents an approach for designing an optimal robot structure using regenerative drive mechanisms that enable energy storage and recovery through ultracapacitors. The authors propose new control and modelling methods that improve the efficiency of energy regeneration and allow direct energy redistribution between robot joints. The study in [15] investigates the major impacts of energy consumption during robot operation, reporting e.g. that 28% of total robotic energy consumption occurs during idle time. As some positions require higher energy consumption due to moments of inertia and gravity, when the robot is not moving it is recommended to set the shortest possible time to turn off the servomotors. Feed-rate is an important factor during motion, also studied in [16], as end-effector feed-rate and resulting joint axes velocities that are too low lead to higher energy consumption because they increase the activation time of the servomotors. It is also noted that linear motion is more energy efficient than joint motion because it minimizes unnecessary changes in velocity and acceleration. In terms of trajectory, continuous motion is preferable as it reduces the number of stops and starts. Friction and temperature also significantly affect power consumption, as friction in the robot joints can account for up to 20% of the total energy consumption, and at low temperatures the lubricant has a higher viscosity, which can increase energy consumption. As temperature increases, friction decreases, leading to lower energy consumption. The robot should therefore operate in the optimum temperature range to minimize frictional losses.

Areas most relevant to the topic of this paper are programming optimization and production process optimization in general. Some of the approaches described in [17] or in [18] focus on robotic cells implementing multiple processes in sequence. The solution presented in latter mainly addresses the issue of efficient scheduling of individual processes, and the proposed method simultaneously optimizes the robot's sequence of movements and the velocity of its movements. A multi-criteria approach is used to find trade-off (Pareto efficient) solutions between energy efficiency and production capacity. The formulation developed through the research is based on Second-order cone programming (SOCP) for accurate small cell scheduling. The heuristic algorithm that was developed allows for efficient generation of Pareto efficient solutions even for larger scale problems. Robot end-effector feed-rate is synchronised with the time requirements of each process and unnecessary waiting (partial waiting) is eliminated, leading to a reduction in energy consumption. Robot velocity control using a convex energy consumption function allows cost minimization while maintaining productivity. The presented tests showed that for two and three machine cells, multi-machine cycles can lead to energy savings of up to 15.4% compared to conventional unit cycles. Another example of an optimization approach is described in [19]. There, the approach is based on the existence of multiple solutions of robot configurations for reaching a point during point-to-point motion in handling applications. The optimal configurations for the given applications are found using a genetic algorithm. The optimization of joint configurations and global scheduling enables more efficient energy utilisation for industrial robots in cyclic tasks. The proposed method is flexible and applicable in real production conditions, with the potential to be implemented in production planning software tools.

Focusing specifically on the individual processes that a robot can perform, a model is needed to predict the energy consumption of industrial robots while they are in motion. Energy consumption models of robots and various technological processes have been intensively studied and developed in the literature. Several detailed procedures and methods have been developed to build these models as described e.g. in [20]. In [21] a comprehensive robot energy consumption model for laser operations was created, including a process energy consumption model. The model is further simplified to operate within the permissible robot end-effector feed-rate range, where it can determine a reasonably accurate prediction of energy consumption with reduced computational requirements. However, it is still a complex model that includes, among other things, the friction parameters of the robot joints to provide the most accurate values possible for the energy consumed during the process. Since most of the energy in high-power laser processes is consumed by the laser itself, the process time of the operation is an important indicator of when the energy consumption is highest. The study in [22] also presents a comprehensive model for calculating the robotic energy consumption, which is further implemented in the off-line preparation of the control program and focuses on optimizing the robot's motion parameters, such as acceleration and feed-rate along the toolpath while it is in motion, to ensure that the energy consumption is as low as possible. Further extensions of this work are described in [23], where a user-friendly interface for easy implementation of the optimization to robotic trajectory planning is developed. However, this approach cannot be applied when precise motion along a continuous toolpath at a specified constant feed-rate of the end-effector's working point is required. Another example of using a complex energy consumption model is described in [24], where e.g. mechanical brakes and other sources of energy losses are modelled. This optimization approach targets robotic cells used in the automotive industry. Power consumption is reduced by optimizing the motion from the last point of the desired trajectory to the home position – once again, however, this is a motion where the desired feed-rate can be varied – as well as by efficiently controlling the brakes of the robot axes. Most physical analytical models are based on equation (1), which is described in detail e.g. in [25], and by means of which, given a known robot mass distribution, position (θ), velocity ($\dot{\theta}$) and acceleration ($\ddot{\theta}$) of the robot's articulated axes, it is possible to determine the required torques in each of the robot's articulated axes (τ) to achieve the desired end-effector motion.

$$D(\theta)\ddot{\theta} + C(\theta, \dot{\theta})\dot{\theta} + g(\theta) = \tau \quad (1)$$

$D(\theta)$ is the robot's inertia matrix, $C(\theta, \dot{\theta})$ is the matrix of centrifugal and Coriolis terms, $g(\theta)$ is the vector of gravitational forces, and τ are the torques at the articulated joints. In the case of a complex continuous trajectory containing a significant number of points, where this calculation needs to be performed at each point, the computational power requirements and hence the computation time increase significantly.

Another approach to calculating energy consumption is to use a data-based/data-driven model based on machine learning principles, using artificial neural networks. The advantage of these models is that, in contrast to the physical models described above, it is not necessary to know all the specific parameters of the individual robot components; however, sufficient data is required to train the model. This approach is in detail described for

example in [26], [27], or in [28] where a Batch-Normalized Long Short-Term Memory (BN-LSTM) network to create an energy consumption prediction model for industrial robots is used. In [29] the goal is to find the optimal operating parameters without requiring complex mathematical modelling of the robot kinematics and dynamics. The approach uses a neural network (BP neural network) to find the relationship between operating parameters (feed-rate, acceleration) and energy consumption. Once the energy consumption model has been created, a genetic algorithm is used to optimize the parameters to find the combination of operating parameters that minimize the robot's energy requirements. Testing was conducted on an Epson C4 robot and according to the authors, the measurements showed that the optimized trajectory can reduce energy consumption by up to 70% compared to the default settings. The authors state that the method does not require detailed knowledge of the structure and control of a particular robot, making it more universally applicable. However, this optimization approach works with point-to-point motion, used in pick-and-place applications where the specific trajectory between defined points is not continuously controlled. The study in [30] describes, in addition to the use of a data-driven model based on the Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) method, robot trajectory optimization to reduce power consumption using an adaptive genetic algorithm. However, it should be noted that in this work, too, the trajectory is planned for industrial robot pick-and-place applications, and not for optimizing a specific robot end-effector continuous desired toolpath. In [31] authors present method, that uses a kinematics-informed neural network architecture to predict the electric consumption of the robot during a manufacturing task as well as path feasibility. The paper suggests using this method further in the real-time applications because its efficient computational time.

In general, complex models are used to predict or simulate the electric energy consumed by a robot in a given application. They are both computationally intensive and require several parameters corresponding to the specific robot. In some cases, these parameters must be determined experimentally, which may further complicate the model synthesis. In trajectory optimization, these models are, in most cases, used in applications (with some exceptions) that do not require precise robot motion along a continuous toolpath but rather point-to-point motion – i.e. pick-and-place applications. When moving the end-effector along a continuous toolpath that contains many points, the use of these models is inefficient due to the complexity of the computation. Thus, there is potential for developing an effective algorithm to optimally adjust the robot and workpiece configuration for operations requiring precisely defined end-effector motion along a continuous toolpath that contains a significant number of points. Such trajectories are encountered in the use of industrial robots for technologies such as waterjet cutting, laser cutting, metal welding and possibly large-format 3D printing. In these cases, it is possible to select power consumption or, for example, productivity as an optimization criterion.

The method developed in this paper, which aims to minimize the robot's power consumption during the required technological operation, uses knowledge of kinetic energy during the robot's movement. The kinetic energy of the robot varies while it is in motion – it does not remain constant, even if a constant feed-rate of the end-effector's working point is desired, because the velocities of the individual robot joint axes are not constant in this case. When the time trend of the kinetic energy during the robot motion is monitored and an effort is made to minimize this trend, the work required to perform the robot motion is reduced, which should correlate with the amount of electrical energy consumed.

There are several reasons why this method works with kinetic energy rather than the full calculation of the required torques (and therefore the required currents) for each articulated axis of the robot:

- It is easier and faster to calculate the kinetic energy;
- When comparing different robot configurations for the same repetitive operation, the difference in kinetic energy should be a sufficient discriminating criterion that incorporates the velocity of each articulated axis and the mass distribution of the robot links for a particular configuration;
- The kinetic energy at each point along the toolpath is an easily quantifiable parameter that is a suitable optimization criterion.

These considerations are all successively verified in this work, offering a novel approach to the optimization of robot and workpiece configurations in the robot's workspace. Another novel contribution of this work is the use of optimization via genetic algorithm for technologies requiring precise continuous toolpath control along a defined trajectory with a defined feed-rate of robot end-effector. A model and post-processor were created in Matlab software to demonstrate and verify this method. An industrial robot combined with a rotary tilt table that can provide up to three redundant degrees of freedom for five-axis technological operations, as it is shown in Fig. 1, was considered for the verification. Specifically, Kuka KR 60 HA and ABB IRB 2600 robots were used for the

experimental testing. Kinematic models of the robots, kinetic energy calculation models and inverse dynamics models were constructed to verify the performance of the proposed method.

Fig. 1. Visualization of the considered robotic cell

The rest of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 describes the proposal of robot model used in the presented method. Two approaches are described in more detail: first, the calculation of the kinetic energy of an industrial robot and second, the inverse dynamic calculation. A comparison of calculation times is presented as well. Section 0 shows the proposed method for optimizing the energy consumption in robot continuous-path tasks and its implementation, and Section 4 describes the experimental validation of the proposed method. Finally, the work is summarised in the conclusion in Section 5.

2. Robot model proposal

While the kinematic equations describe the robot's motion without considering the forces and torques that cause the motion, the dynamic equations explicitly describe the relationship between force and motion. These equations are an important tool in robot design, simulation and planning and visualisation of robot motion, and design of control algorithms [25].

One approach is to use Euler-Lagrange equations. To determine the Euler-Lagrange equations in a particular situation, the Lagrangian of the system (2), which is the difference between the kinetic energy and the potential energy, must be developed. It is then possible to calculate the desired torques using equation (3).

$$\mathcal{L} = K - P \tag{2}$$

$$\frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \dot{\theta}_i} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \theta_i} = \tau_i \tag{3}$$

The final form of this equation for a particular robot leads to rather complex equations for which the inertia matrix and the Christoffel symbols must be calculated. Thus, the entire calculation can be computationally demanding if used in an optimization algorithm, risking unnecessarily inefficient computation time. In this paper, an approach is proposed and tested where only the kinetic energy calculation is used to optimize the power consumption for a selected robotic application, omitting the other steps of the inverse dynamics calculation to reduce the computation time and simplify the synthesis of the robot's power consumption model.

However, there is another method for calculating the robot's inverse dynamics that may be more suitable for numerical computation. This is an alternative formulation of the robot dynamic equations, known as the Newton-Euler formulation, which is a recursive formulation of the dynamic equations. This method is introduced at the end of this chapter and its computational time is compared with the computational time required to calculate the kinetic energy.

2.1. Kinetic energy of the industrial robot

To determine the kinetic energy of the robot in each configuration, it is necessary to know each joint's velocity, position and the mass distribution of the links, i.e. their masses and moments of inertia. The positions can be obtained from the calculation of the inverse kinematics problem, the velocities can be calculated from the desired effector velocity using the Jacobian, and the masses and moments of inertia of the links can be obtained from the robot manufacturer's technical documentation. If this documentation is not available, these values need to be measured, calculated, or, for example, obtained from a CAD model of the robot.

The kinetic energy of a rigid body in space can be expressed as a sum of two components. The first component is the translational energy, which can be described as the translational motion of the body's centre of mass and the rotational energy about the centre of mass. The kinetic energy of a body can therefore be expressed in general terms in the basic coordinate system as (4).

$$K = \frac{1}{2} m \vec{v}^T \vec{v} + \frac{1}{2} \vec{\omega}^T \mathcal{J} \vec{\omega} \quad (4)$$

In equation (4), the vectors \vec{v} and $\vec{\omega}$ are the translational and angular velocity vectors expressed in the basic coordinate system describing the translational velocity of the body's centre of mass and the angular velocity of the body about its centre of mass. Similarly, matrix \mathcal{J} , which is the inertia tensor of the body's centre of mass, is related to the orientation of this system and is therefore dependent on the body's actual configuration. If the constant inertia tensor associated with the coordinate system of the body in question (denoted by c) is to be used, the inertia tensor related to the basic coordinate system can be expressed as (5) using the rotation part of the transformation matrix between the body and the basic coordinate system.

$$\mathcal{J} = R_c^0 I_c R_c^{0T} \quad (5)$$

The inertia tensor of a rigid body is generally a 3x3 symmetric matrix. This matrix can be expressed in the body's coordinate system according to (6). I_{xx} , I_{yy} , and I_{zz} are the principal moments of inertia and $I_{xy} = I_{yx}$, $I_{xz} = I_{zx}$, and $I_{yz} = I_{zy}$ are the products of inertia.

$$I_c = \begin{bmatrix} I_{xx} & I_{xy} & I_{xz} \\ I_{yx} & I_{yy} & I_{yz} \\ I_{zx} & I_{zy} & I_{zz} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

To calculate the robot's kinetic energy, it is necessary to know the inertia tensors of all robot links in their local coordinate systems. These values must either be calculated (if the geometry and mass of each link is known), or obtained from the robot's technical documentation or requested from the robot manufacturer. Another option is to obtain these values from the CAD model of the robot. Most modern CAD programs can determine both the position of the centre of mass and the values of the inertia tensor when the density of the body is defined.

The kinetic energy of the entire robot can be understood as the sum of the kinetic energy of its individual links. The position of the links in space relative to the basic coordinate system always depends on the joint coordinates, just as the translational and angular velocity of the centre of mass of each link depends on the velocity of the joint axes. To determine the centre of mass velocity of each link, the partial form of the Jacobian corresponding to a given link (denoted by i) can be used. Thus, it is always the Jacobian calculated only to the position of the centre of mass of that link. Using equations (7) and (8), it is then possible to determine the translational and angular velocity of the centre of mass of each link.

$$\vec{v}_i = J_i^v(\theta)\dot{\theta} \quad (7)$$

$$\vec{\omega}_i = J_i^\omega(\theta)\dot{\theta} \quad (8)$$

With the known inertia tensor of each link oriented in its local coordinate system according to the modified Denavit–Hartenberg notation (this notation is described in more detail e.g. in [32]), it may be oriented, according to the current robot configuration, to the basic coordinate system using the rotational part of the transformation matrix corresponding to the given link, according to (5). Thus, if equation (4) is further decomposed using equations (7) and (8), the equation describing the total kinetic energy of the six-axis angular industrial robot becomes (9).

$$K = \frac{1}{2}\dot{\theta}^T \sum_{i=1}^6 [m_i J_i^v(\theta)^T J_i^v(\theta) + J_i^\omega(\theta)^T R_i^0(\theta) I_i R_i^0(\theta)^T J_i^\omega(\theta)] \dot{\theta} \quad (9)$$

It can be written in an abbreviated notation as (10), where $D(\theta)$ is a symmetric, positive definite robot inertia matrix. A recursive algorithm can be easily implemented to calculate it.

$$K = \frac{1}{2}\dot{\theta}^T D(\theta)\dot{\theta} \quad (10)$$

2.2. Comparison of calculation times

To verify the statement that the calculation of kinetic energy is indeed more efficient than the calculation of the inverse dynamics problem, in this chapter the calculation time is compared to the calculation of the inverse dynamics using the Newton-Euler method. This method is chosen simply because the kinetic energy calculation is only one of the intermediate steps in the calculation using the Euler-Lagrange equations, and thus the overall calculation using this method must logically take longer.

An inverse dynamic task refers to a calculation where the input is the position – θ , velocity – $\dot{\theta}$, and acceleration – $\ddot{\theta}$, of the joint coordinates, and the output is the required torques τ of each joint axis actuator. An additional advantage of the presented method is that all other reactions in the robot joints are also calculated. Equation (11) describes the forces acting on the link and equation (12) describes the torques. $\vec{r}_{i,ci}$ and $\vec{r}_{i+1,ci}$ are vectors to the link centre of mass, expressed in the link coordinate system. $\vec{r}_{i,ci}$ is the vector from the link coordinate system to the link centre of mass and $\vec{r}_{i+1,ci}$ from the end of the link to the centre of mass.

$$\vec{f}_i - R_{i+1}^i \vec{f}_{i+1} + m_i \vec{g}_i = m_i \vec{a}_{c,i} \quad (11)$$

$$\vec{\tau}_i - R_{i+1}^i \vec{\tau}_{i+1} + \vec{f}_i \times \vec{r}_{i,ci} - (R_{i+1}^i \vec{f}_{i+1}) \times \vec{r}_{i+1,ci} = I_{c,i} \vec{\alpha}_i + \vec{\omega}_i \times (I_{c,i} \vec{\omega}_i) \quad (12)$$

It is apparent that to calculate the forces and torques acting on link i , the forces and torques acting on link $i+1$ must be known. This means that the calculation starts from the robot flange and proceeds with decreasing index i to the robot base, $i = 6, \dots, 1$. It is also clear from the equations that the angular velocity $\vec{\omega}_i$, angular acceleration $\vec{\alpha}_i$ and linear acceleration $\vec{a}_{c,i}$ of the centre of mass of a given link must be known. These quantities, expressed in the local coordinate system of a given link, can be defined using (13), (14) and (15).

$$\vec{\omega}_i = (R_i^{i-1})^T \vec{\omega}_{i-1} + \vec{z}_i \dot{\theta}_i \quad (13)$$

$$\vec{\alpha}_i = (R_i^{i-1})^T \vec{\alpha}_{i-1} + \vec{z}_i \ddot{\theta}_i + \vec{\omega}_i \times \vec{z}_i \dot{\theta}_i \quad (14)$$

$$\vec{a}_{c,i} = (R_i^{i-1})^T \vec{a}_{e,i-1} + \vec{\alpha}_i \times \vec{r}_{i,ci} + \vec{\omega}_i \times (\vec{\omega}_i \times \vec{r}_{i,ci}) \quad (15)$$

As can be seen in (15), to calculate the linear acceleration of the centre of mass of a given link, the linear acceleration of the end of the previous link $\vec{a}_{e,i-1}$ must be known. This can be expressed by equation (16).

$$\vec{a}_{e,i} = (R_i^{i-1})^T \vec{a}_{e,i-1} + \vec{\alpha}_i \times \vec{r}_{i,i+1} + \vec{\omega}_i \times (\vec{\omega}_i \times \vec{r}_{i,i+1}) \quad (16)$$

These relations may be used to construct a recursive algorithm for calculating the required torques at each joint axis. This algorithm must contain two loops. In the first loop, where the index increases, i.e. $i = 1, \dots, 6$, the quantities from equations (13) – (15) are calculated sequentially. In the second loop, where the index decreases, the forces and torques are calculated from the modified equations (11) and (12). The algorithm can thus be summarised as:

- 1) Setting the initial conditions as $\vec{\omega}_0 = \emptyset$, $\vec{\alpha}_0 = \emptyset$ and $\vec{a}_{e,0} = \emptyset$, for increasing index $i = 1, \dots, 6$ a sequential calculation:
 - a. $\vec{\omega}_i$ from equation (13)
 - b. $\vec{\alpha}_i$ from equation (14)
 - c. $\vec{a}_{e,i}$ from equation (16)
 - d. $\vec{a}_{c,i}$ from equation (15)
- 2) Setting the initial conditions either as $\vec{f}_7 = \emptyset$ and $\vec{\tau}_7 = \emptyset$, or as input forces and torques acting on the robot flange and then for decreasing index $i = 6, \dots, 1$ a sequential calculation:
 - a. \vec{f}_i from equation (17) – modification of equation (11)

$$\vec{f}_i = m_i \vec{a}_{c,i} + R_{i+1}^i \vec{f}_{i+1} - m_i \vec{g}_i \quad (17)$$

- b. τ_i from equation (18) – modification of equation (12)

$$\vec{\tau}_i = I_{c,i} \vec{\alpha}_i + \vec{\omega}_i \times (I_{c,i} \vec{\omega}_i) + R_{i+1}^i \vec{\tau}_{i+1} - \vec{f}_i \times \vec{r}_{i,ci} + (R_{i+1}^i \vec{f}_{i+1}) \times \vec{r}_{i+1,ci} \quad (18)$$

To verify the validity of the approach of using only the kinetic energy calculation in the optimization function, a three-axis continuous toolpath containing 6218 points on which a constant end-effector feed-rate is required was created and the kinetic energy calculation at each point of this path was performed simultaneously with the calculation of the required torques using the N-E inverse dynamics algorithm. This toolpath is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Test toolpath for computation efficiency comparison

The resulting calculations were compared using a Matlab software function, i.e. Matlab Profiler, which is used to analyse the efficiency and computation time of the created code. Fig. 3 shows comparison of calculation times between kinetic energy and the inverse dynamics calculation algorithms.

Fig. 3. Comparison of calculation times

Table 1 summarises the execution times of these two algorithms. The kinetic energy calculation is indeed more efficient, in this case by 16.9 %. This advantage is particularly apparent for toolpaths that contain a large number of points.

Table 1

Comparison of calculation times.

Algorithm	Number of trajectory points	Calculation time	Time savings
Kinetic energy	6218	5.386 s	16.9 %
N-E inverse dynamic	6218	6.479 s	-

3. Optimization procedure

The following section describes the optimization procedure using the model described in Section 2. Fig. 4 shows a schematic diagram of this procedure, including the necessary inputs, sub-components and outputs.

Fig. 4. Schematic diagram of the optimization procedure

If an industrial robot that is used, for example, for waterjet or laser cutting, laser or electric arc welding or another technology, is equipped with a rotary tilt table, there will be three degrees of freedom redundant in the case of a five-axis programmed end-effector toolpath. Firstly, rotation around the axis of the work tool, and secondly rotation and tilting of the table, in the case of a suitable type of work head that allows it to rotate freely around the tool centre point (TCP). An image of this degree of freedom, which represents the ability to freely rotate the effector around its work axis, is shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Redundant degree of freedom – rotation around the tool axis

For optimal performance of the technology implemented by the robot in regard to the selected criterion, it is imperative to find a position or orientation of the workpiece in its workspace and a suitable angle of rotation around the tool axis so that the designed criterion is minimized. If it is possible to define a function for the selected manufacturing operation using the workpiece's orientation relative to the robot in the Cartesian coordinate system and the redundant rotation angle about the tool axis as the input, and the designed criterion as the output, it is possible to search for the minimum of this function using a suitable optimization algorithm. As this function can generally be highly nonlinear, genetic algorithms are well suited for finding its minimum. In this case, the criterion is energy consumption. As stated earlier, the method developed in this paper aims to find a redundant parameter configuration that minimizes the kinetic energy cumulated over time. Thus, the resulting proposed integral criterion for evaluating a given position is based on the calculation of the kinetic energy at each point of the trajectory for a given configuration. The total value of the proposed criterion is the integral of the kinetic energy over the duration of a given technological operation (19).

$$\kappa_{el} = \int_{t_0}^{t_n} K dt \quad (19)$$

The purpose is therefore to find a configuration in the range of motion of the rotary table and robot when it is rotating around the tool axis in which the criterion is minimized. In other words, if the criterion can be defined as the function of the mentioned redundant parameters, i.e. (20), it is possible to search for its minimum using a suitable optimization algorithm – a genetic algorithm in this case.

$$\kappa_{el} = f_0(A_s, C_s, \varphi_e) \quad (20)$$

The proposed algorithm serves as an input function for the optimization algorithm. The inputs are the rotation of the table and the rotation angle around the tool axis. The algorithm then retrieves the CL data of the toolpath (X, Y, Z coordinates and I, J, K tool orientation vector). Next, the desired linear and angular velocity of the robot flange needs to be determined based on the set desired feed-rate of the process operation, which is given in the CL data. The required angular velocity is based on the change in tool orientation over time in the case of a five-axis operation; it is null in case of a three-axis operation. Fig. 6 shows the tool movement between points P1 and P2. Referring to the figure, it is important to note that the angular velocity $\vec{\omega}_{2,tool}$ shown is not the tool rotation velocity, e.g. in milling technology, but the velocity of the effector rotation around the tool axis (if this movement is realised), i.e. the change of the redundant rotation angle C in time between points P1 and P2.

Fig. 6. Translational and angular velocity of the tool centre point (TCP)

The quantities shown in Fig. 6 can be successively expressed as – \vec{v}_{tool} tool linear velocity between points according to (21), where v_{f_prog} is the desired feed-rate of the given technological operation in m/s. The required

movement time t_0 between the points can be calculated according to (22) using the distance between points P1 and P2 and the feed-rate. From the comparison of the tool vectors at points P1 and P2, the spatial angle $\varphi_{1,2}$ between them can be determined according to (23). Next, the first contribution to the tool angular velocity $\vec{\omega}_{1,tool}$ can be determined according to (24) and the second contribution to the tool angular velocity $\vec{\omega}_{2,tool}$ according to (25). Thus, the total required angular velocity of the TCP $\vec{\omega}_{tool}$ at the point P1 is (26).

$$\vec{v}_{tool} = \frac{P2 - P1}{|P2 - P1|} \cdot v_{f_prog} \quad (21)$$

$$t_0 = \frac{|P2 - P1|}{v_{f_prog}} \quad (22)$$

$$\varphi_{1,2} = \cos^{-1}(\vec{tool}_{P1} \cdot \vec{tool}_{P2}) \quad (23)$$

$$\vec{\omega}_{1,tool} = \frac{\vec{tool}_{P1} \times \vec{tool}_{P2}}{|\vec{tool}_{P1} \times \vec{tool}_{P2}|} \cdot \frac{\varphi_{1,2}}{t_0} \quad (24)$$

$$\vec{\omega}_{2,tool} = \vec{tool}_{P1} \cdot \frac{C_{P2} - C_{P1}}{t_0} \quad (25)$$

$$\vec{\omega}_{tool} = \vec{\omega}_{1,tool} + \vec{\omega}_{2,tool} \quad (26)$$

Once the linear and angular velocity of the TCP and the vector from the TCP to the robot flange expressed in the basic coordinate system $\vec{t}_{e,f}$ are known, the angular velocity $\vec{\omega}_f$ (27), linear velocity \vec{v}_f (28), angular acceleration $\vec{\alpha}_f$ (29) and linear acceleration \vec{a}_f (30) of the robot flange can be determined.

$$\vec{\omega}_f = \vec{\omega}_{tool} \quad (27)$$

$$\vec{v}_f = \vec{v}_{tool} + \vec{\omega}_{tool} \times \vec{t}_{e,f} \quad (28)$$

$$\vec{\alpha}_f = \vec{\alpha}_{tool} \quad (29)$$

$$\vec{a}_f = \vec{a}_{tool} + \vec{\alpha}_{tool} \times \vec{t}_{e,f} + \vec{\omega}_{tool} \times (\vec{\omega}_{tool} \times \vec{t}_{e,f}) \quad (30)$$

These values are then used to calculate the velocities and accelerations of the robot's articulated joint axes. Fig. 7 shows a diagram of the function for evaluating the toolpath using the energy criterion. This function is the input for the optimization. The output of the optimization algorithm is the optimum rotation around the effector axis in addition to the optimum rotation and tilting angles of the rotary tilt table.

Fig. 7. Diagram of the function used in the genetic algorithm

4. Experimental validation

The following chapter provides an important experimental validation of the described method. First a five-axis toolpath in Cartesian space is evaluated, where an angular velocity of the tool is present. Therefore, as described in Section 0, there can be a substantial demand on the robot flange velocity and acceleration that can, based on the desired feed-rate of the end-effector, lead to limit velocities and accelerations of the robot joint axes. In this type of motion any changes in robot and workpiece initial configuration can lead to significant changes in the dexterity of robot motion during the selected operation which can, in conclusion, substantially affect the robot's energy consumption. The second case studied in this chapter works with end-effector three-axis movement in Cartesian space. Generally, in that case, all of the robot's joint axes are still moving simultaneously but the demand for the flange velocity and acceleration is much lower than with the five-axis trajectory. Therefore, the goal in that case is to find out whether the developed method is applicable even for these types of technological operations and, if so, under what conditions.

4.1. Five-axis toolpath

A five-axis freeform cutting experiment of a sheet metal part was designed for initial validation of the functionality and efficiency of the method for minimizing power consumption. Such parts may be cut by a waterjet or laser cutting head, and the head may be carried by an industrial robot. If the machine configuration includes a rotary tilt table for clamping the part, such a work cell can look, for example, like the machine shown in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8. Considered work cell to demonstrate the functionality of the proposed method

The real work cell where the experiment was carried out does not contain a rotary tilt table, but this can be emulated for the experiment by tilting and moving the workpiece in space. In this case, the monitored variable is the electric current required for the robot movement, while the power consumption of the process itself is not monitored, and the table only performs the initial indexing of the workpiece. It is therefore possible to set the toolpath and just orient the workpiece coordinate system in the desired way – thus emulating the table rotation and tilting. The workpiece itself does not need to be present in the workspace at all, and the technology performed by the work head does not need to be active for this test: only the movement of the robot needs to be implemented. Therefore, a work cell with a KR 60 HA industrial robot carrying a CEAD E25 work head, shown in Fig. 9, was used for the practical verification. This robot is controlled by a Sinumerik 840D control system using the RunMyRobot Machining option.

Fig. 9. The actual robot used for the experiment

The geometry of the metal sheet to be cut can be arbitrary, but a geometry combining various elements such as arcs and sharp corners was chosen to better demonstrate the functionality of the developed algorithm. Fig. 10 shows the test workpiece and toolpath. The required feed-rate along the toolpath was set as $v_{f_prog} = 1000 \text{ mm/min}$ (0.0166 m/s) and a thin cutter with a diameter of 1 mm representing a water or laser beam was chosen as the tool, which can also be seen in Fig. 10. Since such parts are commonly cut with a technological bevel, the resulting toolpath is five-axis. As described above, the algorithm accounts for the rotation and tilting of the rotary tilt table and the rotation about the tool axis as redundant degrees of freedom that can be optimally adjusted.

Fig. 10. The test workpiece

To confirm the assumption that the proposed kinetic energy calculation method for comparing the individual positions converges to the same optimal position as the more complex and computationally demanding inverse dynamics calculation method, both the kinetic energy criterion values and the mechanical work (32) calculated from the immediate power value (31) determined by the Newton-Euler calculation of the inverse dynamics method were calculated for the selected operation, both for a selected range of redundant angles of rotation about the tool axis values φ_e .

$$P = \sum_{i=1}^6 \tau_i \cdot \dot{\theta}_i \quad (31)$$

$$W_{mech} = \int_{t_0}^{t_n} P dt \quad (32)$$

The angle range was selected as -60° to 1° and the step as one angular degree. Thus, only a change in the redundant rotation angle at a single base position of the rotary tilt table was considered to enable determination of the progression of the change in the monitored criteria and of whether the progressions were sufficiently consistent. As shown in Fig. 11, the progression of the criteria does indeed match and the optimal angle determined by the kinetic energy calculation method is 43° (a) while the angle determined by the N-E inverse dynamics calculation method is 44° (b). This can be considered a sufficient match and, considering the advantages of the kinetic energy calculation method (namely the calculation time and easier implementation), using it for the complete optimization – with the addition of the change of the rotation and tilting angles of the rotary tilt table – is a favourable solution.

Fig. 11. Comparison of calculation methods – kinetic energy (a), inverse dynamics (b)

The function that serves as an input to the genetic algorithm was described in Section 0. Fig. 12 shows the flow of the optimization after thirty generations. The results of the algorithm calculation are the rotation and the tilting of the rotary tilt table (defining the rotation and displacement of the part's coordinate system relative to the robot) and the rotation about the tool axis, defining the configuration in which the kinetic energy of the robot motion is minimized. The global optimization toolbox from Matlab software was used in this case.

Fig. 12. Genetic algorithm calculation

The resulting configurations to be compared with each other are the default, non-optimized configuration, where the rotary tilt table is not rotated in any way, the optimized configuration determined by the genetic algorithm, along with three other configurations randomly chosen in the robot and table workspace which can be used to verify that the solution that was found is indeed optimal. Table 2 shows the parameter values, A_s being the tilting of the table, C_s the table rotation and φ_e the redundant angle of rotation about the tool axis. The calculated criterion values for these observed configurations are also listed.

Table 2
Tested robot configurations.

Configuration	Parameters	Criterion value
Default	$A_s = 0^\circ, C_s = 0^\circ, \varphi_e = 0^\circ$	$\kappa_{el} = 12.88$
Optimized	$A_s = 1^\circ, C_s = -122^\circ, \varphi_e = 87^\circ$	$\kappa_{el} = 7.94$
Test 1	$A_s = 28^\circ, C_s = 48^\circ, \varphi_e = -37^\circ$	$\kappa_{el} = 11.58$
Test 2	$A_s = -3^\circ, C_s = 55^\circ, \varphi_e = -10^\circ$	$\kappa_{el} = 12.04$
Test 3	$A_s = -18^\circ, C_s = -42^\circ, \varphi_e = 71^\circ$	$\kappa_{el} = 12.17$

For the test manufacturing operation at the sample work cell, all monitored configurations were set up in Siemens NX CAM software. The tilting and rotation of the rotary tilt table were emulated by tilting and moving the workpiece coordinate system, the default configuration is shown in Fig. 13 (a) and the optimized configuration in Fig. 13 (b). This step was mainly used to visualise the motion, given that the NC programs were generated from Matlab.

Fig. 13. Comparison of the settings of default (a) and optimized (b) configurations

For correct validation of the functionality of the proposed method, it was first necessary to verify that each calculated quantity from the simulation corresponds to the real robot motion. It was possible to check whether the calculated velocities of the robot's joint axes in all configurations corresponded to the real velocities measured from the robot's control system thanks to the trace function of the Sinumerik 840D control system, which controls the robot through the RunMyRobot Machining option. It is possible to read these values online because in this version of the Sinumerik control system, the controller sends the desired velocities of the joint axes to the Kuka robot's native control system after interpolation of the trajectory.

4.1.1. Default configuration

Fig. 14 shows the computed velocities of each joint axis from the simulation and Fig. 15 shows the actual measured velocities for the default configuration. At first glance, the difference in the second section of the toolpath is noticeable, where the interpolator tries to maintain the desired end-effector feed-rate on the toolpath. In the

simulation, the acceleration constraints of each joint axis are considered and the same values as in the robot control system are used. However, no deviation from the desired effector toolpath is allowed in the simulation, while a tolerance of 0.05 mm is set in the control system.

Fig. 14. Computed values of the rotational joint velocities for the default configuration

Fig. 15. Actual measured values of the rotational joint velocities for the default configuration

While the toolpath tolerance will allow the interpolator to better follow the desired end-effector feed-rate, it will cause a deviation from the desired toolpath and, in this case, a rather significant undercut of the part. Fig. 16 shows the reconstructed end-effector toolpath from the measured velocities from the control system. The highlighted box in the figure shows this undesirable effect, which in a real situation would most likely cause an unacceptable defect in the manufactured part.

Fig. 16. Reconstructed end-effector toolpath for the default configuration

4.1.2. Optimized configuration

In the next phase, a similar evaluation of the joint velocities was performed for the optimized configuration found using GA. It is immediately apparent that a more convenient workpiece set-up not only causes the real velocities to approach the ideal velocities for a given toolpath (but still including acceleration constraints), but also results in a reduction of the peak values of velocities in the critical section of the observed toolpath. Fig. 17 shows the joint velocities from the simulation and Fig. 18 shows the joint velocities from the robot measurements.

Fig. 17. Computed rotational joint velocities for the optimized configuration

Fig. 18. Actual measured rotational joint velocities for the optimized configuration

This also results in a more precise end-effector toolpath reconstructed from the real measured velocities, as shown in Fig. 19. The highlighted box in the figure again shows the toolpath of the observed critical section without undercutting, which means, among other things, that it is possible to produce higher-quality parts without defects compared to the non-optimized configuration.

Fig. 19. Reconstructed end-effector toolpath for the optimized configuration

The most important part of the verification is to validate the described approach by measuring the robot's power consumption for each configuration. A Chauvin Arnoux Qualistar CA 8335 electrical analyser, shown in Fig. 20 (a), was used for this measurement. The analyser was plugged into the electrical box, directly to the power cable for the robot. The measurement was carried out in this way, as the values of the currents for each axis cannot be read from the Sinumerik control system when using the RunMyRobot Machining option. The connection of the meter to the electrical box of the control cabinet is shown in Fig. 20 (b).

Fig. 20. The power consumption analyser device (a) and measurement set-up (b)

Power analyser transfer software was used to collect data from the measurements, from which it is possible to obtain a record of the data in csv format and subsequently process the data in Matlab software. After obtaining the relevant data from both toolpath runs in the default configuration (ten times in a row) and in the other configurations (also ten times in a row), this data was evaluated. Table 3 shows the total power consumption for each configuration, and again the values of the computed criterion for each configuration are also shown for reference. The comparison of the measured values among the configurations under study shows that the one found using the genetic algorithm is indeed the optimal one, and energy savings are achieved compared to the default configuration and the other test configurations as well.

Table 3
Comparison of data measured in each configuration.

Configuration	Criterion value	Energy consumption	Percentage difference – criterion	Percentage difference – consumption
Default	$\kappa_{el} = 12.88$	55.76 Wh	–	–
Optimized	$\kappa_{el} = 7.94$	50.40 Wh	38.35%	9.61%
Test 1	$\kappa_{el} = 11.58$	54.86 Wh	10.09%	1.61%
Test 2	$\kappa_{el} = 12.04$	54.37 Wh	6.52%	2.49%
Test 3	$\kappa_{el} = 12.17$	57.17 Wh	5.51%	–2.53%

A comparison of a single toolpath pass for the default and optimized configurations is shown in Fig. 21. In the critical section of the toolpath, there is a significant peak in the power input in the default configuration, which corresponds to the peak in the calculated kinetic energy trace. Thus, it can be concluded that the kinetic energy

trace indeed correlates with the real power consumption during the robot motion, and the proposed criterion is therefore a suitable tool for evaluation of the power consumption of the different configurations.

Fig. 21. Comparison of a single toolpath pass for the default and optimized configurations

Fig. 22 shows the full measurement of ten toolpath passes for the default and optimized configurations. This figure shows, among other things, that the optimized configuration has a shorter total time, so that in addition to reduced power consumption, productivity is increased, resulting in more efficient production.

Fig. 22. Full measurement of ten toolpath passes for the default and optimized configurations

The operation time (ten passes of the selected toolpath) in the default configuration is 437 s, while in the optimized configuration it is 420 s. It is therefore evident that using the method developed in this paper, the proposed five-axis operation, designed to produce a complex shaped part, has resulted in a 9.61% reduction in power consumption and a 3.98% reduction of manufacturing (processing) time. The increase in productivity in this case has an additional positive effect on power consumption. Although the process itself (abrasive waterjet, laser beam)

is not considered in the test performed, these technologies generally consume a larger amount of energy than the industrial robot when moving along the toolpath. Therefore, the increase in productivity results in a further energy savings because the technology used during the production process is activated for a shorter time. Another positive effect of the optimization is the improved toolpath accuracy, which eliminated undesirable undercutting of the part.

4.2. Three-axis toolpath

To verify the possibility of a wider application of the optimization method, an experiment was carried out to weld a part with WAAM technology using an ABB IRB 2600 robot and ABB IRP A two-axis positioner. The experiment involved welding blades on a cylindrical blank, see Fig. 23. The blank's orientation to the torch is set by rotating the positioner, so that the movements of the robot in the Cartesian coordinate system are three-axis.

Fig. 23. WAAM robotic set-up

The purpose of the experiment was to determine whether the optimization method is suitable for these types of technological operations and, if so, under what conditions. Due to the defined rotation of one axis of the positioner to rotate the workpiece, only two degrees of freedom are redundant in this case, namely the positioner's tilting angle and end-effector's rotation angle around the tool axis (welding head). To find the optimal setting of these parameters in terms of power consumption, a robot model was created according to the procedure described in sections 2 and 0. CL data were generated for the given operation and the optimized configuration of the robot and positioner in terms of power consumption was found using a genetic algorithm, namely $A_s = 120^\circ$, $\varphi_e = -20^\circ$. This configuration is shown in Fig. 24 (b). Subsequently, a workpiece was welded in the default configuration, i.e., $A_s = 90^\circ$, $\varphi_e = 180^\circ$, shown in Fig. 24 (a), with the measured total power consumption of the work cell, and then a second workpiece was welded in the optimized configuration. The process conditions were set in the same way for both configurations; the desired end-effector feed-rate was set to $v_{f_prog} = 200 \text{ mm/min}$ (0.0033 m/s). In this case, a very low end-effector feed-rate was used and therefore it was not expected that the robot movements would contribute significantly to the total energy consumption.

Fig. 24. Welding in the default configuration (a) and in the optimized configuration (b)

The resulting measured power consumption traces are shown in Fig. 25. By integrating the traces over time, the power consumption in both configurations was calculated. In both cases, the measured consumption was 2060 Wh. No savings were achieved, most likely due to the excessively low feed-rate of the end-effector movement and therefore of the robot joint axis movements. At such low velocities, there are no noticeable differences between the robot motions in the default and optimized configurations during movement along the programmed toolpath.

Fig. 25. Measured power consumption traces in both configurations

Therefore, another test was performed with the welding process switched off, but with an increased end-effector feed-rate, specifically $v_{f_prog} = 1800 \text{ mm/min}$ (0.03 m/s). Again, the power consumption of the entire work cell was measured and the power consumption in the default and optimized configurations was evaluated. Here, the effect of the optimization became apparent, as shown in Fig. 26, where the trace of the energy consumption of a section of the toolpath is visible. The peaks in the displayed trace correspond to the individual table rotations and the movements are identical in the two configurations; the areas between these peaks correspond to the robot and table movements and are therefore subject to evaluation of savings. As the figure shows, a 3% savings is achieved at this end-effector feed-rate even for this kinematically less demanding type of motion in the three axes of the Cartesian coordinate system. The total power consumption in both configurations is listed in Table 4.

Fig. 26. Comparison of energy consumption of a section of the toolpath

Table 4
Comparison of data measured in both configurations.

Configuration	Criterion value	Energy consumption	Percentage difference
Default	$\kappa_{el} = 12.35$	171 Wh	–
Optimized	$\kappa_{el} = 12.07$	166 Wh	3%

Therefore, it can be concluded from the experiment carried out with WAAM welding technology that the optimization method can have an effect even in the case of a simpler three-axis robot toolpath (in the Cartesian coordinate system); however, the end-effector feed-rate must be set sufficiently productively so that the kinematic capabilities of the robot are engaged, if the technology allows it.

5. Conclusion

With the developed approach, the workpiece’s position and orientation in space relative to the robot were shown to have a significant impact on power consumption and, in some cases, even on production productivity. Using the presented method, it was possible to find the optimized configuration of a work cell with an industrial robot and a rotary tilt table to reduce power consumption and increase production productivity just by optimally setting the rotary tilt table and adjusting the optimal redundant angle of the end-effector. A kinetic energy criterion was used as the differentiation factor between the different configurations and then a genetic algorithm was used to find the optimal one. For a five-axis toolpath case, the improvement between the default position and the optimized position was a 9.61% reduction in power consumption and a 3.98% reduction of manufacturing (processing) time. For a

three-axis toolpath with a feed-rate with a sufficiently productive setting, the optimized configuration demonstrated a 3% reduction in power consumption compared to the default configuration. It was shown that the kinetic energy calculation is more efficient than the complete inverse dynamics calculation and is also a sufficiently accurate criterion for evaluating toolpath variants in terms of power consumption. Thus, new approaches have emerged that may be superior in many respects to the standard methods used so far. The impacts of the electricity consumption savings achieved may include economic savings in production, thus reducing the price of the manufactured part, reduced environmental impacts of production, as well as further economic savings in production due to more efficient use of manufacturing (processing) time and further reduction in electricity consumption due to shorter involvement of highly energy-intensive processes. A patent application has been filed for this optimization method based on the integral kinetic energy criterion. The results are applicable to a wide range of parts and technologies across various industries where industrial robots are employed.

Additional challenges emerged during this work and subsequent research, highlighting opportunities to further enhance the proposed methodology for reducing power consumption in robotic applications. The method could be extended by incorporating additional optimizable parameters, such as the feed-rate of the technological operation, where feasible. Moreover, the power consumption model may be improved by including factors like joint friction and the energy usage of auxiliary systems, ideally without a significant increase in computational time.

As the method is designed for offline robot programming, future work should focus on developing a user-friendly library or script that can be integrated into standard robot toolpath design software. This would make the method more accessible to users and operators in industrial settings and facilitate its practical adoption.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Tomas Kratena: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Visualisation. **Petr Vavruska:** Methodology, Resources, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Jiri Sveda:** Conceptualisation, Methodology, Investigation, Resources, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration. **Franz-Jakob Matschnig:** Methodology, Resources, Data curation, Writing – review & editing. **Friedrich Bleicher:** Resources, Supervision, Project administration. **Pavel Zeman:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

Tomas Kratena and Petr Vavruska have patent #2025-56 pending to Industrial Property Office of the Czech Republic. Other authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

The presented research was supported by the European Union under the project “ROBOPROX - Robotics and Advanced Industrial Production”, reg. no. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004590.

Data availability

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16537271>

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